

ERIC Forum Implementation Project

ERIC Forum Website

Work Package 5 - Deliverable 5.3

Deliverable no	D5.3
Deliverable Title	ERIC Forum Website
Contractual delivery month	01.05.2019
Responsible Partner	CERIC-ERIC
Author(s)	Salma Baghdadi, CERIC-ERIC Nicoletta Carboni, CERIC-ERIC Ornela De Giacomo, CERIC-ERIC Jana Kolar, CERIC-ERIC

Executive summary

This deliverable represents the ERIC Forum website, which is the major online communication channel used for all target audience categories and the general public.

Copyright notice

This work by Parties of the ERIC Forum Implementation project Consortium is license under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Document log

Issue	Date (yyyy-mm-dd)	Comment	Author/partner
	30.04.2019	D5.3 ERIC Forum Website	Salma Baghdadi, CERIC-ERIC

Background

The ERIC Forum website, www.eric-forum.eu, is the major tool of the ERIC community. It includes information about both the ERIC Forum, and the ERIC Forum Implementation Project. This information is structure in a way to keep the website visitors aware of the purpose and progress of the ERIC community’s work and activities.

Approach

The structure of the ERIC Forum Website was presented to the project partners at the Kick Off meeting in Amsterdam on 31st January – 1st February. It is organized as follow:

Advancing ERICs

The ERIC Forum Implementation Project brings together 20 established European Research Infrastructure Consortia (ERICs) and 3 ERICs in preparation to strengthen their coordination and enhance collaborations between the partners. The strategic approach of the ERIC Forum will contribute to address critical challenges and develop best practices.

The **major objectives** of the ERIC Forum Implementation Project are to:

- **strengthen coordination and networking** reinforcing the informal ERIC network or its successor framework,
- **support the organisation of specific meetings**, targeted thematic workshops focusing on shared challenges such as the development of internal procurement rules, harmonised reporting, VAT exemption practices, insurances and pensions policies and training of governance bodies representatives;
- support ERICs in preparation, based on **best practices**;
- support **common communication and outreach activities** and strengthen external representation of ERICs' as a stakeholder in consultations and other policy actions that could affect them.

LATEST NEWS

The ERIC Forum website will be continuously be updated with information related to:

- The overview of all ERICs, by clusters.
- The history of the ERIC Forum and the Memorandum of Understanding,
- The advances of the various activities within each Work Package,
- The events organized by Research Infrastructures which would be of interest to the community,
- The job opportunities available among ERICs,
- Pubic deliverables,
- Documentation generated throughout some of the work packages of the project,
- Information related to the ERIC regulations and more.

The ERIC Landscape by Cluster

Life Science

Eu Openscreen
 the European Infrastructure of Open Screening Platforms for Chemical Biology-develops novel small chemical compounds that elicit specific biological responses on organisms, cells or cellular components.

<http://www.eu-openscreen.eu> [Robert-Rössle-Str. 10, 13125 Berlin, Germany](#)

The website’s search system allows the visitor to find information in a user-friendly way. For example, it is possible to search for ERICs by cluster. Also, the website incorporates a question form which help the visitor ask questions about specific topics, which would then be redirected to the working group responsible for the selected topic.

The screenshot shows the ERIC Forum website interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the ERIC FORUM logo on the left and links for HOME, ABOUT, THE PROJECT, NEWS, and a search icon. A blue button labeled "RESERVED AREA" is also present. Below the navigation bar is a banner with a word cloud background and the text "ERIC Forum - Contact List".

The main content area is titled "ERIC Forum Contact List:" and includes the following text:

For general inquiries, contact us at: info@eric-forum.eu

For questions related to specific topics within the ERIC Forum project, you can contact us by submitting the form below.

The contact form is titled "Submit your question/comment here" and contains the following fields:

- Name (text input)
- Surname (text input)
- Address (text input)
- Country (dropdown menu)
- Email (text input)
- Institution (text input)
- Topic (dropdown menu)
- Comment / Question (text area)

At the bottom of the form, there is a checkbox labeled "Accept *Privacy Policy." and a blue "SEND" button.

Moreover, the website will include a reserved area which will redirect to the internal repository platform of the ERIC Forum, SharePoint, in order to facilitate the access for project partners.